

Problems and Solutions for an Inclusive Ecosystem For Indian Women Entrepreneurs

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Date of Submission: 02-05-2023

Date of Acceptance: 11-05-2023

ABSTRACT

Women entrepreneurial endeavors continue to garner worldwide attention. There has been a lot of research done on women entrepreneurs, but very little is known about them. This is surprising considering that women are one of the populations of entrepreneurs whose numbers are growing at the fastest rate and play a significant role in innovation, job creation, and economic growth all over the world. In spite of obvious progress, women in every nation trail men in business ownership and economic independence. Gender discrimination, conflict between work and family, difficulty raising capital, lack of infrastructure, unstable Business, Economic, and Political (BEP) environments, lack of training and education, and personality differences are some of the obstacles that women entrepreneurs in developing nations face. According to the study, unstable BEP environments and financial constraints must be addressed as top priorities. This review focuses on entrepreneurship as a career choice for women, the motivations and career paths followed by women entrepreneurs, the attitudes and behaviors associated with successful ventures, the issues that persist, and the policies that conspire to keep women's businesses few and far between will all be examined. It also describes about the laws and practices that have helped and hindered women entrepreneurship, as well as ways to reframe the issues and change policies which provides policymakers with guidance on to create an environment that encourages the success of women entrepreneurs and bridges the gap between theory and practice in entrepreneurship.

KEYWORDS: women entrepreneurs, Gender discrimination, BEP, Policymakers, Guidance.

I. INTRODUCTION

New ideas and opportunities that have the potential to engage disadvantaged and excluded members of society have gained momentum thanks to concepts like social entrepreneurship and inclusive innovation (Bruton et al., 2015; George et al., 2012). In order to enable underprivileged populations to participate not only as potential customers but also as suppliers and producers, social entrepreneurs who target emerging economies are employing inclusive strategies such as the creation of job opportunities (Grobbelaar et al., 2019).

Gender plays an increasingly important role in understanding the factors that influence and encourage entrepreneurship and innovation. Gender has been taken into account in a number of studies when looking at various measures of innovative activity, like how many women file patents (Hunt et al., 2012). Following a more in-depth discussion of these kinds of studies, one striking and consistent finding is that, despite an increase in women's participation in activities related to innovation and entrepreneurship, significant gaps remain before women can hope to be on par with men. According to a recent report (Milli et al., 2016), women are not expected to achieve patent parity until 2092 at the current rate of progress (since 2000).

Due to their feminine competencies of being more empathetic, emotional, and compassionate, women are better suited to employ inclusive strategies and lead social enterprises (Clark Muntean & Ozkazanc-Pan, 2016). These female business owners are crucial to the improvement of society and the reduction of poverty (Kimbu & Ngoasong, 2016). However, since most studies on women in business are based in developed countries,

these claims need to be proven from an emerging economies perspective (Yadav & Unni, 2016). Additionally, dealing with institutional gaps, extreme poverty, a lack of entrepreneurial education and skills, and the low social and cultural status of women are just some of the many challenges that female entrepreneurs face in emerging economies' insane and uncertain environment (Yadav & Goyal, 2014).

WOMEN'S ROLE IN INNOVATION AND ENTREPRENEURSHIP

Women's lower participation in innovation and entrepreneurship has larger socioeconomic indications than just a social inequality that needs to be addressed. Take into consideration the fact that, according to some studies, women devote 90 cents of every additional dollar of income to "human resources" for their families—such as education, nutrition, and health care—in comparison to 30 to 40 cents for men (Shah & Saurabh, 2015b). As a result, it will have a direct and positive effect on families, communities, and society as a whole if there are more women entrepreneurs (Vanderbrug, 2013).

Today, a growing number of women are stepping forward to take part in various economic endeavors. To begin the process of economic development in any nation, women's entrepreneurship is, without a doubt, of the utmost importance. There is no specific field in which women are not employed. Women make up about half of the population, and their participation in nation-building is essential (Hyderabad Angels, 2022).

India has excellent opportunities for women's entrepreneurship in this era of globalization, startup booms and digitalization. Women entrepreneurs hail from every region of the country and come from all walks of life. The role of women has evolved over the past few decades and is moving in the direction of much-needed improvement. In today's industry 4.0, women can come up with creative solutions to problems and make sound decisions. Through innovative solutions, female entrepreneurs have created numerous new jobs for themselves and others (Hyderabad Angels, 2022).

Women entrepreneurs are doing exceptionally well and exceeding market expectations in some of businesses. Women have a lot of success in business and industry, as well as in aeronautics, science, military, medicine, law, space travel, and police. Women who run their own

businesses have a few traits that make it easier for them to put their innovative and creative ideas into action every day (Hyderabad Angels, 2022).

When it comes to starting their own businesses, women place a high value on their networking, communication and organizational abilities. In addition, they are expert at achieving work-life balance. A successful woman entrepreneur should be able to support at least ten additional women. Indian women's economic independence has increased over the past few decades (Hyderabad Angels, 2022).

Women's barriers to entry, which prevent them from realizing their full entrepreneurial potential, must also be considered in any discussion about women in innovation. Lack of basic education, especially in developing economies, a lack of access to new markets and a lack of market knowledge, a lack of support networks and mentorship, a lack of technical and business knowledge, and a lack of access to information and communication technologies like the Internet and social media are just a few of the factors that contribute to this problem. Other factors include (i) issues related to gender-based and cultural constraints, which are especially relevant in a country like India, (ii) insufficient access to capital (Shah & Saurabh, 2015a).

REASONS WHY WOMEN START THEIR OWN BUSINESSES

Women are now accepted in every industry, by overcoming all the barriers. In India, women's entry into business can be traced back to their kitchen activities, particularly 3P's, Powder, Pickle, and Pappad. Women, on the other hand, began shifting their focus away from the traditional three Ps and toward the three modern Es—electronics, energy, and engineering. Most women who enter the business world do so for the reasons of their expertise, knowledge, and adaptability. A woman who accepts a challenging job to meet her own needs and become financially independent is a woman entrepreneur. Entrepreneurial women are able to contribute values to both family and social life because they have a strong desire to do something good. Women are aware of their own rights, characteristics, and workplace situations thanks to media. The opportunities and challenges offered to women in the digital age are expanding so rapidly that job seekers are becoming job creators. Due to a traumatic event like a divorce, corporate glass ceiling, pregnancy-related discrimination, a family member's health, or an economic hardship like a layoff, many women start their own businesses.

However, as more women choose to leave the corporate world to determine their own futures, a new talent pool of women entrepreneurs is emerging today. They are doing well as interior decorators, publishers, designers, exporters and garment manufacturers and they are still looking into new ways to get involved in the economy (Koneru & Head, 2017). The reasons for a woman to become an entrepreneur are shown in the following flow chart (fig 1).

Figure:1 Women as Entrepreneur

According to the recent studies, women in India start their own businesses out of a desire for career challenge and self-determination, and they anticipate receiving the respect, recognition, and self-esteem that come with both. Entrepreneurship is primarily a survival instinct that inspires women to establish businesses. Dismal economic conditions, high unemployment rates, and divorce all encourage women to start their own businesses. Women are defying societal norms in order to survive, desperate to feed their families (Bhatnagar et al., 2012a).

Entrepreneurship is a process that is very personal and subjective. Changing political, economic, social, and cultural factors necessitate a series of experiences, situations, and events for an individual to develop into an entrepreneur. Individual entrepreneurs are compelled to alter their personal living conditions as a result of these diverse circumstances. The group of women who own and run a business is not uniform. Whether a woman can become an entrepreneur in her society is determined by cultural and social norms. There are obvious restrictions; Others hide behind patriarchal traditions in societies that discourage female entrepreneurship. Regarding business ownership, Jehan Sadat said, "There are those who still realize that they too can enter the race." However, despite numerous obstacles, women nevertheless manage to engage in entrepreneurial endeavours. The question that should

be asked instead of "can she" or "why does she" when entrepreneurship is at stake is "how she does" and "where can she go for help (Bhatnagar et al., 2012a)."

In both the formal and informal sectors, the process of starting and running a new business can be extremely challenging for a woman entrepreneur because she frequently lacks the skills, education, and social support system necessary to facilitate her efforts (Bhatnagar et al., 2012a).

CHALLENGES SPECIFICALLY FACED BY WOMEN ENTREPRENEURS A SOCIETY DOMINATED BY MEN

The field of entrepreneurship has been dominated by men for a long time; this is slowly changing now, but there is still a long way to go. Despite the fact that we have successful female entrepreneurs like PepsiCo chairman Indira Nooyi, women are still regarded as physically and emotionally weak (Aslam et al., 2013).

INSUFFICIENT RESOURCES

Finance is the business's lifeblood, but a lot of Indian women don't have any assets in their names. Due to the lack of collateral security, they have difficulty arranging financing. Because of the money they need, they have no choice but to wait for their family (Aneke et al., 2017).

WORK-LIFE HARMONY

Women are expected to play a leading role in household management and family care around the world. They are expected to do both when they start their own business, and they are not given any exceptions from the family. Getting administrative and financial support from the family is also not guaranteed (Mwobobia, 2012).

A LACK OF KNOWLEDGE

Around 3.5 percent of women in India are illiterate, making illiteracy a major issue. Even if they want to start a business, they don't because they don't know much about the latest business trends or the market. They are having difficulties in business (Mwobobia, 2012).

A LACK OF DRIVE

When running a business, motivation is very important. Women sometimes lack the drive to start their own business for the above said reasons (Chinomona, E et al., 2015)

WORK-LIFE BALANCE OF WOMEN ENTREPRENEUR

A family's financial situation is not solely determined by men's earnings. Women are also blame for the family's improved economic well-being. Women defy cultural and social stereotypes and exhibit both push and pull factors to achieve social recognition and identity. They started their own business to improve their financial skills. Women are motivated by factors of push and pull. Recognition, self-worth, and the desire to work on one's own rules and regulations, earn more money, and become independent are all pull factors. Job dissatisfaction, the financial situation of the family, the education and care of the child, and the illness or death of the husband are all push factors. As a result, they use their entrepreneurial skills to overcome their family's economic crisis and improve their children's lives. Women are emerging as a powerful force in the age of high technology that policymakers cannot ignore. Women's entrepreneurship has been recognized for its ability to generate wealth, jobs, and solutions to societal issues. Maintaining a work-life balance means balancing one's personal and professional lives. In the United Kingdom, the concept of "work-life balance" was first used in the late 1970s to describe a person's ability to maintain a healthy work-life balance. Both family and work are important to both men and women. Women are also taking on the role of breadwinner when they earn money for the benefit of their families, which upsets the balance in their families. Women's participation in entrepreneurial endeavours helped to maintain a work-life balance (Agarwal & Lenka, 2015).

WORK-LIFE BALANCE (WLB) ISSUES OF WOMEN ENTREPRENEURS

Indian women are now engaged in a variety of traditional as well as non-traditional entrepreneurial activities, such as founding financial institutions, educational institutions, and entertainment companies, after overcoming many inherent disadvantages caused by the deeply ingrained traditional mindset and strict etiquette. Many of these women are required to play multiple roles in their families in addition to their challenging work as entrepreneurs (Fig 2). Being a parent, spouse, and caretaker are examples of these roles; managing the daily chores of the home; and offering social and community services. Women must also take care of their own health and other personal responsibilities, which are frequently overlooked due to time constraints and role overload. The absence of WLB and the emergence of numerous WLB issues

result from each of these circumstances (Mathew & Panchanatham, 2011).

Figure 2: Diverse roles of women entrepreneur

CHALLENGES INDIAN WOMEN FACE ON THEIR WAY TO ENTREPRENEURIAL SUCCESS IN THE 21ST CENTURY

The ability of women to start and run a business is still misunderstood in many households. Family members continue to question women's capacity for decision-making. Women are denied access to family property and a significant amount of tangible security. As a result, banks also hesitate to lend to them. Credit is rarely available to women (Yunus, 2006). Due to preconceived notions about women, banks are hesitant to accept household goods as collateral. Women also lack access to information, contacts, and expertise that will enable them to discover new markets (Mueller, 2004). Women also require networking to build contacts and improve business performance and expansion (Rao, 2014). Women rarely realize their entrepreneurial potential beyond the essentials necessary to support their families (Basu, 2015). Even if a woman is a career woman or an entrepreneur, she still must fulfill multiple social and familial roles. Women's quest for equal opportunities is being hampered in new ways by globalization. As a result of worsening working conditions and an insecure working environment, particularly in rural areas, the expanding global economy has resulted in benefits that are not being shared equally, which has led to an increase in economic and gender inequality as well as the feminization of poverty. It is necessary to devise strategies to enhance women's capabilities

and prepare them to combat the negative social and economic effects of globalization (Chitrao, 2020).

Women in leadership roles are only desired by 20% of businesses. The survey of 2,250 adults found that 69% of respondents agreed that women are just as good leaders as men and that women make better leaders than men. According to half of those polled, women are more honest than men, and honesty was rated as the most important leadership quality. According to the respondents, intelligence was the second most important quality in a leader; 14% of respondents said that women are less smart than men, while 38% said that women are smarter than men (Kulkarni, Nirzar, 2011).

How Indian women deal with conflict between their responsibilities in the family and in the business. They must unavoidably choose between family obligations and business demands. There are numerous studies on how successful women managers and leaders "managed." Three methods were described in one such study: Limit and prioritize, assuming that you can't have it all. Keep in mind that it is possible to balance work and family obligations, but not simultaneously. This includes, for instance, postponing or rushing into having children. Get assistance with family caregiving by delegating it. Every woman was required to make some kind of compromise because of the study's finding that there was no ideal compromise among the three approaches. The primary research participant, a woman entrepreneur, acknowledged employing all three of the above strategies (Gersick & Scholar, 2013).

REASONS FOR WOMEN ENTREPRENEURS' SLOW PROGRESS IN INDIA

The expansion of women's entrepreneurship has been restricted because of the difficulties and constraints they face. The following are the primary obstacles that women entrepreneurs face:

The fact that women entrepreneurs are discouraged the most. Their path to business success is based on a kind of male-dominated, patriarchal social order. Male chauvinism is still prevalent in many parts of the country. Male members consider financing female-run businesses to be a big risk. Women are viewed as "abla," or weak in every way. Women's lack of equality with men in a male-dominated society makes it difficult for them to enter the business world. Women entrepreneurs face fierce competition from men entrepreneurs, who can easily participate in the promotion and development space and easily market their products to the organized sector as well as their male counterparts. Women business owners will ultimately be forced out of

business because of this competition. Women are more likely to make mistakes while working on their projects because they lack self-assurance, willpower, mental toughness, and an optimistic outlook. Society and family members are reluctant to support their entrepreneurial expansion.

In India, women live a safe life. They are even less educated, economically unstable, and dependent, all of which make them less able to handle the risks and uncertainties associated with a business unit. One of the reasons they failed is the outdated social outlook that discourages women from starting businesses. In contrast to men, women's mobility in India is extremely limited for a variety of reasons. They are subjected to social pressure that prevents them from prospering and achieving success in the field of entrepreneurship. A single woman still gets looked at suspiciously when she asks for a room. They are forced to give up their desire to survive in business entirely due to the time-consuming process of starting a business and the sexist attitudes of officials toward women. In both developed and developing nations, women are also prevented from becoming successful entrepreneurs by the obligations they have to their families. Financial institutions discourage women entrepreneurs because they believe they can always quit their jobs and return to being housewives. Indian women place a greater emphasis on relationships and family ties. Women who are married must strike a delicate balance between family and work. The family's support of women in the business process and management is also critical to its success.

Women's personal and family obligations can sometimes make it hard for them to succeed in business. Only a small number of women can prioritize and effectively manage both their homes and their businesses. Women's participation in business is also influenced by husbands' educational levels and family histories. Women are forced to give up on the idea of achieving greatness in the business world because of the lack of appropriate support, cooperation, and encouragement from their own family members and the people in the outside world. They constantly inspire a lot of pessimism in them and make them believe that family, not business, is a better fit for them. The Entrepreneurial Development program provides training to many women without an entrepreneurial bent. Through tests, interviews, and other methods, the aptitude of women who receive training from a variety of institutions needs to be confirmed.

Some business operations' high production costs hinder the growth of female entrepreneurs. Women who run their own businesses are discouraged from expanding into new markets by factors like the installation of new equipment during capacity expansion. Women-owned businesses tend to be small, and it can be difficult for them to obtain the necessary information about technology, training, novel programs, concessions, alternative markets, and so on. Only a small number of female business owners use technology, and they are also restricted to word processing programs on computers. They rarely use the advanced software that is available, such as statistical software like SAP, accounting software like TALLY, animation software like 3D MAX, the internet, and so on. They are also unaware of the financial assistance that is available in the form of incentives, loans, programs, and so on. by the financial sector's institutions. Therefore, genuine efforts to support female entrepreneurs may not reach those in rural and underdeveloped areas.

Women were found to be less motivated to achieve goals than men. Women who participate in business operations and run a business are less motivated to succeed and advance because they lack confidence and education. In addition to the issues previously mentioned, women entrepreneurs may face additional serious issues such as inadequate infrastructure, high production costs, societal attitudes toward women's modern business outlook, and low business needs. Women also typically launch businesses ten years later than men. It has been suggested that traditional socialization, motherhood, and a lack of managerial experience all delay entry into entrepreneurial careers (Koneru et al., 2017).

SWOT ANALYSIS

STRENGTH & WEAKNESSES

The term "women entrepreneur" refers to a self-assured, innovative, and creative woman who can create employment opportunities for others while maintaining her personal, family, and social lives while initiating, establishing, and operating the business. Self-employment is favoured by women because of their desire for social recognition and difficulty securing suitable employment (Singh, 2014). Women are forced to give up on the idea of achieving greatness in the business world because of the lack of appropriate support, cooperation, and backing from their own family members and the people in the outside world. In both developed and developing nations, women are also prevented from becoming successful entrepreneurs by their responsibilities to their families. Women were found

to be less motivated to achieve goals than men. The fact that they are women is the greatest obstacle for female entrepreneurs (Singh, 2014).

OPPORTUNITY & THREATS

Women are heavily involved in business dealings and instil entrepreneurial values. Eco-friendly technology, biotechnology, IT-enabled businesses, event management, the tourism industry, telecommunications, plastic materials, mineral water, herbal and health care, food and vegetable processing, and biotechnology are among the upcoming business opportunities for women entrepreneurs. In the rural areas, women entrepreneurs take advantage of new opportunities for ice cream, channel products, papads and pickles, and ready-made clothing (Singh, 2014). Lack of technology and a fear of expansion. Women fear making mistakes while working on their projects because they lack self-assurance, willpower, mental fortitude, and optimism. Officials who are not cooperative and credit discrimination. Dealing with male laborers, insecurity, and inadequate infrastructure. Indian women value relationships and family ties (Singh, 2014).

FEMALES CONTRIBUTIONS TO GLOBAL MARKET

Women who run their own businesses bring a lot to the global market (Vishnuvarthini et al., 2016). Female business owners have demonstrated the capacity to construct and uphold the relationships and networks built over time, to effectively communicate and organize then exercise financial restraint and to promote sensitivity to cultural differences and to be aware of the requirements of their environment. The businesses of women are qualitatively distinct from those of men.

According to research, female business owners establish a distinct culture of their own. Delivering services to traditionally unmet needs is often the focus of female-owned businesses. Sally Helgesen, the author, said that before deciding, women managers frequently look for information, exchange ideas with others, and allow information to solidify. To make up for what they perceive to be their flaws, female business owners exhibit a remarkable willingness to seek education and business guidance (Bhatnagar et al., 2012b).

II. SUGGESTIONS FOR THE GROWTH OF WOMEN ENTREPRENEURS

To increase the number of women entrepreneurs and their participation in

entrepreneurial endeavours, appropriate efforts from all sectors are required. Being an entrepreneur basically means having control over one's life and activities, and for women entrepreneurs to overcome their paradoxes, they need confidence, independence, and mobility. To give women the power to take advantage of opportunities and overcome challenges in business, the following recommendations are made.

Women entrepreneurs should be encouraged, supported, encouraged, and supported in every way possible. The goal of a large-scale awareness campaign should be to educate women about the various business opportunities available to them. To raise women's overall personality standards, efforts should be made to raise education standards in general and to make effective provisions for their training, practical experience, and personality development programs. Develop professional competencies in managerial, leadership, marketing, financial, production process, profit planning, and other skills through the organization of training programs. This will inspire women to start their own businesses. Women's community to receive vocational training that teaches them about production management and the production process.

Women's polytechnics and industrial training institutions should be used for skill development. Workshops that combine training and production put skills to use. To support the growth of entrepreneurship, educational institutions should collaborate with a variety of government and non-government organizations, primarily to plan business projects, to assist women in facilitating interaction with other female entrepreneurs, trade fairs, industrial exhibitions, seminars, and conferences (both local and international should be organized) and to encourage women in business to engage in industrial endeavours, soft loans and subsidies should be made available. Both small and large-scale businesses should receive more working capital assistance from financial institutions. At the local level, providing women entrepreneurs with a microcredit and enterprise credit system. The less fortunate could get money through a variety of government programs and incentives designed to encourage entrepreneurs in the state. Examples include the Khadi and Rural Village Industries Scheme, the Prime Minister's Rozgar Yojana, and so on (College, 2012).

Women entrepreneurs may encounter difficulties in the beginning, but they must persevere, have faith in themselves, and not give up halfway through. Efforts by a variety of non-governmental organizations (NGOs) and government agencies to

disseminate information about policies, plans, and strategies for the advancement of women in industry, trade, and commerce. Women entrepreneurs ought to take advantage of the various government programs.

Women should try to keep up with the times by taking advantage of the latest technological advantages. For women to become proficient in all aspects of business management, ongoing education and training are necessary. Self-help groups of women entrepreneurs can mobilize resources and pool capital funds to assist women in the field of industry, trade, and commerce. This can also play a positive role in solving this problem. This can help women excel in the decision-making process and develop a good business network. To fully comprehend the differences between men's and women's entrepreneurship, it is necessary to examine women's entrepreneurship at both the individual level (the decision to become self-employed) and the firm level (the performance of women-owned and-managed businesses). To establish forums across India for discussing issues, grievances, and complaints regarding obstacles to women entrepreneurs' economic progress. To make decisions that are favourable to women entrepreneurs and to take a firm stance against policies or strategies that impede their economic development.

Therefore, the issues that women face can be resolved by strictly following the measures. Women shouldn't expect easy success in business. Women's participation in a variety of economic activities does not diminish their responsibilities to the family; rather, it adds to the family's income. Women's work has become more difficult and time-consuming. Let us all work together to assist women in rediscovering her (College, 2012).

SOLUTIONS FOR DEVELOPING WOMEN ENTREPRENEURS IN INDIA

Women's participation is essential to the continued growth and development of entrepreneurship. It is true and applicable to all nations that women entrepreneurs play a significant, albeit smaller, role in business in various regions of the country. As a result, women need a supportive environment in which to actively engage in entrepreneurial endeavours. There is a pressing need for women in India to encourage a greater number of women to become entrepreneurs through the active and supportive efforts of promotional, regulatory, and nongovernmental agencies. It is encouraging to note that the Indian government has developed a variety of employment generation and training

programs for women to help them start businesses (Kaviarasu, 2018) (Rani, 2022).

STEPS TAKEN BY THE GOVERNMENT

Since independence, women's advancement has been a government policy goal. Prior to the 1970s, the concept of women's development primarily focused on welfare. In the 1970s, the welfare approach was replaced by a development approach that recognized the development process's mutually reinforcing nature. The 1980s saw the adoption of a multidisciplinary strategy with an emphasis on three fundamental areas: employment, education, and health. Women were given priority in every industry, including the SSI industry. Women's economic contributions through self-employment and industrial ventures have received increased attention from both government and non-government organizations (Sharma et al., 2013).

Several welfare programs for women were planned for the First Five-Year Plan from 1951 to 1966. A few steps in this direction were taken with the establishment of the Central Social Welfare Board, the organization of Mahila Mandals, and Community Development Programs. Women's empowerment was closely integrated with the overall strategy of intensive agricultural development programs in the second Five-Year Plan, which ran from 1956 to 1961.

Female education was a major welfare measure supported by the Third and Fourth Five-Year Plans (1961-66 and 1969-74). The Fifth Five-Year Plan, which ran from 1974 to 1979, emphasized providing women in need of income and protection with training. This plan was implemented at the same time as the Report of the Committee on the Status of Women in India and the International Women's Decade. Under the Ministry of Social Welfare, the Women's Welfare and Development Bureau was established in 1976.

From 1980 to 1985, the Sixth Five-Year Plan saw a clear shift from welfare to development. It recognized that women's lack of access to resources was a significant obstacle to their development. Gender equality and empowerment were emphasized in the Seventh Five-Year Plan, which ran from 1985 to 1990. For the first time, qualitative aspects like instilling confidence, raising awareness of rights, and training in skills for better employment were prioritized. Through Panchayati Raj institutions, the Eight Five-Year Plan (from 1992 to 1997) emphasized women's empowerment, particularly at the Grass Roots Level.

A Women's Component Plan strategy was implemented in the Ninth Five-Year Plan (1997-

2002), with at least 30% of funds and benefits allocated to women-related sectors. Through the implementation of the recently adopted National Policy for Empowerment of Women (2001) and a rights-based approach, the Tenth Five-Year Plan (2002-07) aims to empower women and ensure their survival, protection, and development. Over 27 programs for women are currently being administered by various departments and ministries within the Indian government. Some examples include:

Training of Rural Youth for Self-Employment (TRYSEM)

Entrepreneurial Development programme (EDPs)

Women's Development Corporations (WDCs)

Marketing of Nonfarm Products of Rural Women (MAHIMA)

Assistance to Rural Women in Non-Farm Development (ARWIND) schemes

Working Women's Forum

NGO's Credit Schemes

Micro & Small Enterprises Cluster Development Programmes (MSE-CDP).

Non-governmental organizations (NGOs) are contributing equally as much to women's empowerment as the government and its various agencies. There are some gaps, despite the coordinated efforts of governments and NGOs. Certainly, we have made significant progress toward women's empowerment, but the road ahead is challenging and demanding.

III. CONCLUSION

This paper surveys and positions the imperatives looked by women business visionaries. It compiles constraints to provide insight into the obstacles that women entrepreneurs in developing nations face. It identifies seven major obstacles that women entrepreneurs face: constraints brought on by personality-based constraints, gender discrimination, work-family conflict, financial constraints, a lack of infrastructure support, unfavorable BEP environments, a lack of training related to entrepreneurship, and others in order to assist policymakers in making informed decisions regarding the allocation of resources in priority areas, the aggregated constraints are then ranked.

The findings indicate that the difficulties faced by female entrepreneurs are more severe and that these difficulties are made worse by the adverse conditions that are prevalent in developing nations. It is difficult for women entrepreneurs to start and run their own businesses in this setting. As a result, it is critical that policymakers are aware of this and contribute to the creation of an environment that

encourages women to start their own businesses. The paper provides policymakers with a plan to improve the environment for women's entrepreneurial growth. Scholars will need to examine successful projects involving women in entrepreneurship in a variety of countries in the future to comprehend the reasons behind their success. This is significant because, although we currently know what hinders women's entrepreneurship, additional evidence regarding what makes women's entrepreneurship successful is required. These insights can be used by researchers to examine policy initiatives in depth and offer suggestions for increasing their impact.

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